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The Role of Managers in the Gastronomy Field Amidst the Pandemic

Abstract

Gastronomy is the academic exploration of the interplay between food and culture, encompassing the culinary expertise required to create and present sumptuous and delectable dishes, the distinctive cooking methods associated with specific geographical areas, and the scientific principles underlying optimal nutrition. A person who has extensive knowledge and appreciation of fine food and drink is referred to as a gastronome. A gastronome is someone who actively combines both theoretical and practical aspects of the study of gastronomy. Practical gastronomy encompasses the practical application and scholarly examination of the process of preparing, producing, and serving various cuisines and beverages from many global cultures. Theoretical gastronomy provides a foundation for practical gastronomy. It pertains to a systematic and methodical approach centered around recipes, procedures, and cookbooks. Food gastronomy pertains to the study of food and beverages and their origins. Technical gastronomy complements practical gastronomy by giving a methodical way of evaluating gastronomic subjects.

Keywords: Gastronomy, Pandemic-COVID-19, Manager, Patrons, Servers.

INTRODUCTION

In this paper, I aim to examine the challenges faced by managers in the field of Gastronomy during a pandemic, focusing on the Municipality of Gjilan as a case study. I am particularly interested in gaining a comprehensive understanding of the issues encountered by both managers and workers in cafes and restaurants in the previous year and the current year.

In summary, managers are accountable for overseeing and managing the overall operations of the restaurant or cafe on a daily basis, ensuring the completion of various tasks. However, managers actively strive to enhance the appeal and enjoyment of their profession while relinquishing the tedious aspects. They make an effort to prioritize their interactions with clients or suppliers and engage in conversations with them mostly over coffee. However, overseeing a café or restaurant entails much more than just that. Managers must consistently reiterate the same information on a daily basis to assure the achievement of the intended outcomes.

The purpose of the research

Frequently, the responsibilities of restaurant management are misconstrued, and it appears that restaurant owners lack a clear understanding of the actual tasks that managers are required to perform. In contemporary times, it appears that restaurant managers are exhibiting a lackadaisical approach by relinquishing some responsibilities that are expected of them. We are thus elucidating the recommended job of restaurant management.

Consider a traditional factory supervisor whose responsibility it is to meticulously oversee a manufacturing line, ensuring that every worker is positioned appropriately, performing their tasks accurately, and meeting the necessary performance standards. The majority of his daily labor consists of one particular chore, and it cannot be described as an engaging or stimulating activity. However, it is essential. The role of a restaurant manager is similar to the one mentioned earlier. The restaurant managers are required to assume responsibility for overseeing all aspects of service, including monitoring customer flow, ensuring proper supply quantities, supervising kitchen operations, addressing delays in order delivery, maintaining appropriate room temperature, and investigating any lapses, such as the failure to provide water.

While some may disagree, a manager should ideally fulfill the role of a parent or babysitter for their restaurant crew. Although not always enjoyable, if the manager effectively fulfills their responsibilities, they will ultimately experience the benefits of achieving success. Managers are responsible for overseeing all tasks and responsibilities at all times. It is imperative to consistently prompt the workers to fulfill their responsibilities. Similar to inquiring from your children each evening prior to bedtime whether they have performed the act of brushing their teeth, Refusing their request does not warrant punishment or reprimand, as that is the role of parents.

To verify, to recall, and to ensure the smooth progress of their offspring. Managers should likewise inquire whether they have surrendered their mobile phone and do not possess it in their pocket, among other things.

Another example of how to comprehend the function of restaurant management is to compare it to the role of an orchestra conductor. Despite the instrumentalists' proficiency and many rehearsals, the conductor continues to fulfill his role. He perceives the orchestra from the perspective of the audience, thereby always predicting the actions that the players ought to take. The conductor issues instructions

to all performers, providing guidance on the musical requirements of the moment and indicating which instrumentalists should prepare to play. Similarly, the manager perceives his personnel from the perspective of customers, preemptively anticipating their demands and requirements. The manager must maintain a constant presence and bear the primary responsibility for the restaurant's performance. While every staff member has the option to neglect or overlook their responsibilities, the manager is held to a higher standard and is not afforded the same leniency. He is responsible for memorizing and monitoring everyone's tasks continuously, as well as evaluating their performance.

The gastronomy industry is facing a significant challenge in its struggle for survival as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic.

According to the Guinness Book of World Records, the Botin restaurant in Madrid, Spain, which is 295 years old, is currently facing challenges in its survival due to the socio-economic issues arising from the COVID-19 pandemic.

The user's text is empty. Spain remains the epicenter of the pandemic in Europe, causing a complete halt in travel and exacerbating the challenges faced by the restaurant industry due to stringent restrictions.

More than 40,000 restaurants, bars, or cafes nationwide were compelled to shut down due to their inability to withstand the economic turmoil triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic.

The restaurant "Botin" has been operating in Madrid since 1725. Despite its advantageous position in the industry, thanks to its reputation, experience, and capacity, the restaurant has suffered significant losses owing to the epidemic.

Antonio Gonzalez, a member of the third generation of the Spanish family that has been managing the restaurant since the 1930s, stated to Anadolu Agency (AA) that even during the Spanish Civil War, the restaurant remained open as his grandfather continued to work. However, due to the COVID-19 state of emergency declared from March 14 to June 21, the restaurant was closed in accordance with the decisions made.

He stated that, notwithstanding the state of emergency, they diligently opened the bakery, which has been in operation for almost 300 years and is regarded as the "crown jewel" of the restaurant.

"There are two factors contributing to this situation. Firstly, antique ovens pose significant issues when left closed for extended periods of time. We had to maintain its heat to retain the aroma. Secondly, it holds a romantic appeal for us to heat the oven on a daily basis," explained Gonzalez. The user's text is empty. He characterized the effect of COVID-19 on the Botin restaurant as a "dreadful and unforeseen transformation." On an average day, our restaurant used to accommodate over 600 patrons. However, this figure has now dwindled to 60. Out of our total workforce of 75 employees, 63 are currently on temporary leave with work grants, while only 12 are actively working. As a result, we are incurring a monthly loss ranging from 50,000 to 60,000 euros. The individual in charge expressed concerns that we could sustain this situation for a maximum of 1-2 years.

Gonzalez stated that the majority of their clientele consists of tourists that travel to Madrid from both domestic and international locations. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, many visitors have ceased to arrive.

He stated that they had implemented all the procedures mandated by the legislation to combat the infection.

Gonzalez mentioned that they were included in the "Guinness" book of world records as the oldest

restaurant in the world. Without any request from Gonzalez themselves, a British customer started this recognition in 1987.

"Prior to our arrival, it was situated at a restaurant in Paris." "To obtain this title," reiterated Gonzalez, "one must consistently possess the identical name, occupy the same location, and never terminate."

This restaurant gained international renown following its reference by the renowned American author Ernest Hemingway in the concluding section of his debut novel, "The Sun Also Rises." Numerous writers have also depicted their characters on the premises of this establishment. Furthermore, it is worth noting that the esteemed painter Francisco de Goya worked as a dishwasher at this restaurant prior to embarking on his artistic career.

Famous people like Ava Gardner and Woody Allen have dined at the restaurant, which is well-known for its traditional Spanish cuisine.

The gastronomy industry has been greatly impacted by the pandemic.

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted Kosovo's economy, as it has done globally. The government's preventive measures to curb the virus have resulted in the suspension of numerous industries within the country. Consequently, the income of many businesses has been drastically reduced.

According to a study by the Institute for Free Market Economics (IETL) and the Association of Gastronomists, 76.2% of companies in the Kosovo gastronomy sector will go out of business. The primary concern of business owners is the mounting debt owed to suppliers, with 75.9% of respondents stating that they will be unable to pay outstanding invoices and fulfill other financial obligations towards them.

Based on a study conducted by IDRA Research and Consulting in Kosovo, over 50% of the businesses surveyed ceased their operations as a result of government regulations (81%), a decrease in customer demand (24%), and challenges in meeting employee salary obligations (16%). Merely 50% of the businesses reported maintaining full wage payments to their employees throughout these measures.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the government of Kosovo has implemented stringent measures to restrict the movement of individuals and the functioning of businesses. These measures were enforced from March to the end of May, with the objective of minimizing the number of COVID-19 cases in Kosovo. Sectors significantly impacted by the pandemic include gastronomy, large markets, and the hotel industry. Even businesses and services that were permitted to operate, such as markets, pharmacies, and bakeries, were obligated to adhere to rigorous hygiene protocols.

The GAP Institute conducted an analysis of the initial effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. In April, a total of 32,377 individuals were newly registered as job seekers, resulting in a cumulative count of 37,392 female job seekers at the Employment Agency during the first four months of 2020. Notably, 16,820 of these job seekers are women.

As per the report "Economic shock after the COVID-19 pandemic" by the Association of Certified Accountants and Auditors of Kosovo, if the pandemic extends beyond June, the situation will deteriorate. More than 60% of businesses will face significant challenges in continuing their operations, either operating at limited capacities or being unable to continue at all. Consequently, there will be a need for personnel layoffs.

IMPLEMENTING BUSINESS CONTINUITY STRATEGIES DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

1. Amidst ambiguity, the finance function has the ability to generate value and enhance its position as a strategic business ally. With our CPA and Licensed Global Management Accountant credentials, we possess the necessary knowledge and expertise to effectively mitigate risks and spearhead recovery initiatives for our organizations, enterprises, and communities.

2. The International Association of Certified Professional Accountants, which represents the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA®) and the United Kingdom's Chartered Institute of Management Accountants (CIMA®), offers news, resources, and up-to-date guidance through their Coronavirus Resource Centers. Regularly visit this website to remain informed about the latest developments on the coronavirus and to acquire knowledge about upcoming events, such as the complimentary webinars I will be conducting with prominent finance executives in the upcoming weeks. This series aims to offer expert perspectives on business planning, equipping you with the necessary knowledge to effectively guide your organization during this crisis. An outlined strategy consisting of five sequential steps to ensure uninterrupted business operations

3. During the initial broadcast of this series (also accessible as a podcast), Chris Kite, Oracle's vice president of global strategy, discussed the company's method for ensuring uninterrupted business operations, which commences with the implementation of a Business Continuity Plan (PVB/BCP). Verify whether your firm possesses a disaster recovery plan in the absence of one. If there is no existing one, it is necessary to initiate the creation of a new one from the beginning. To maximize the success of your PVB, it is crucial to follow these five steps: Initiate a business impact study.

4. This analysis can assist your firm in determining and evaluating the potential impacts of the coronavirus on business operations. This procedure entails doing a gap analysis to evaluate your organization's preparedness for uninterrupted operations. When conducting this analysis, take into account the influence on the subsequent interest groups:

Personnel: The labor force should be your utmost priority. The current management of your workforce can significantly influence employee loyalty and retention in the long run. Begin by identifying the processes that are of utmost importance and the staff personnel responsible for carrying them out. Subsequently, ascertain whether these procedures necessitate execution at the company's premises or if they may be carried out remotely. Additionally, contemplate any measure that enables the majority of your corporation to operate in a remote manner. It is imperative to promptly initiate the development of contingency plans, as a portion of your personnel may become ill as a result of the virus.

The organization's ability to respond to and support its clients during these moments will play a vital role in establishing long-term loyalty. An error has the potential to result in enduring harm to one's reputation. Thoroughly track the levels of consumer debt and consistently evaluate their creditworthiness. Utilize non-traditional credit ratings to assess whether a consumer will pose continued challenges after normal conditions are restored, rather than relying on current standard credit scores.

Suppliers - In light of the disruption to global supply chains, it is imperative to identify the supplies or suppliers that are essential for maintaining operational continuity. Conduct a comprehensive evaluation of all your contractual agreements with suppliers, thoroughly comprehend the potential ramifications, and ascertain alternative strategies to sustain your business operations in the event of non-delivery of goods by any of your suppliers. This is the opportune moment to reassess and reevaluate all aspects. The present moment presents an opportune occasion to question conventional thought. Promote and

foster innovation and creativity.

For the subsequent phase, it is necessary to generate models for both the "worst case" and "most probable" situations. This offers a sufficient array of outcomes for the firm to contemplate. By examining the major stakeholders and the risks associated with them, it is possible to determine the potential strategic, operational, and financial results that may occur during the next three, six, or twelve months. The Global Licensed Management Accountants scenario planning tool is an excellent resource to assist you in navigating through this process.

5. During this stage, it is imperative to analyze the scenarios established in the preceding step in order to discern any potential new dangers. This will assist you in constructing robust scripts. Additionally, it is important to take into account other possible hazards, such as financial, strategic, operational, and external risks, and assess the probability of their occurrence. The CGMA Risk Heat Map (Global-CGMA Risk Heat Map) might provide valuable guidance in this undertaking.

Ensuring the extent and effectiveness of organizational reach and communication.

Establish a cross-functional pandemic response team if your organization does not already have one. This will guarantee that the organization is in agreement and working towards the same important goals. Additionally, it is imperative to obtain the necessary authorizations to implement the succession plan in compliance with governance standards.

Engaging in communication with stakeholders is a crucial component of any continuity plan. Determine the subject matter and regularity with which you wish to engage with interest groups. Developing and launching dedicated websites that provide resources and assistance for employees, consumers, investors, and other stakeholders is highly advantageous.

A successful business continuity plan also emphasizes the key performance indicators (KPIs) of essential processes. There should be a higher frequency of measuring and monitoring liquidity, sales, shares, etc. on a daily and/or weekly basis. Conduct data analysis to promptly address evolving hazards. It is imperative to strive for the implementation of ongoing prediction in crucial operations and promptly make any required modifications. As previously said, liquidity is crucial. Equally significant is the labor force, the capacity to consistently cater to customers, along with the upkeep of production lines and the supply chain.

ISSUE DESCRIPTION

Has the pandemic had a detrimental impact on the discipline of Gastronomy?

The global COVID-19 epidemic has had a detrimental impact on the global economy, leading to the closure of numerous large firms. Our country has also experienced significant economic losses, resulting in the closure of businesses across various sectors.

The majority of these firms are small family enterprises, with the most impacted being those in the gastronomy sector, including hotels, restaurants, bars, and nightclubs. According to the Association of Gastronomists, there are approximately 7,000 businesses in imminent danger of bankruptcy. Many workers rely solely on the gastronomy industry for their income. This sector employs a significant number of people in our country, specifically 30,000 individuals, which accounts for 10% of the local

economy. It is important to note that the gastronomy sector is tightly intertwined with the agriculture industry in our country. Our farmers primarily focus on producing food items for gastronomy, including milk, meat, fruits, and vegetables.

METHODOLOGY

In order to execute the process, I opted to utilize the principal approach.

I have chosen to employ the primary methodology since I intend to develop a self-prepared questionnaire comprising 10 inquiries. These questions will be directed at several premises managers, from whom I will obtain the corresponding responses.

He hopes that the chosen methodology will successfully attain the needed objectives. A concise account of the inaugural establishment, a café.

The business, known as 'West Pub', has been functioning since 1993 and is a family-owned establishment. It is situated in Gjilan, namely near the city stadium and the newly constructed square.

Intentions or decisions made to achieve specific goals or objectives.

During this step, we will address the formulation of inquiries and hypotheses and ultimately draw conclusions based on the data obtained from the questionnaire that I have devised.

The questions pertain to the third phase of the issue description, specifically addressing the resolution of the main question and one of the proposed hypotheses.

The research inquiry is: Has the pandemic had an adverse impact on the sector of gastronomy?

The questionnaire I have produced is also applicable for the primary approach, which we have determined to be more precise as the responses were obtained directly from two managers of two bars operating in the city of Gjilan.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

This chapter serves to consolidate the key findings of the entire study in order to provide a more comprehensive explanation of the research. The role of managers in the gastronomy industry during the pandemic has been crucial due to the numerous challenges they have faced. Particularly in recent times, with government-imposed measures, managers have been compelled to make difficult decisions, including the unfortunate necessity of laying off a significant portion of their staff. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that despite the significant decline in workload, they have persevered and actively sought alternative avenues to provide their services, such as implementing take-away and delivery options.

Based on the literature study conducted in this diploma thesis, it is evident that the pandemic has had a profoundly detrimental impact on both the economy of Kosovo and the well-being of its population. This is mostly manifested through its adverse effects on many economic sectors, including:

The production sector, the private sector, the distribution sector, the financial sector, and numerous other sectors.

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